
Cultural Identity Crisis in the Novel Love's Not Time's Fool by Vikas Sharma

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Abstract:

Identity has been a buzzing word in the field of cultural values. Everyone talks about Morality and Scholastic in real life. We don't follow what we preach. We all are aware of our social and cultural responsibilities. We tend to grab the opportunities and show how pure we are in the context of others. The world is full of materialistic things and desires. We have become some sort of inanimate things like robots we work with, and we have lost our emotions. As we see in *The Waste Land* by T.S Eliot, even cousin Marie became the victim of hunger and lost her identity. The characters of Richa Pandit and Abhilash have shown the hidden voices of society in the form of instincts. How does a married woman lure a young protagonist into losing his moral and cultural identity? The characters resemble it as a daily activity or a job to be in bed with someone. This reminds us of the clerk in *The Wasteland*. After the meal, her lover performs the activity with her because she is bored. People earn money, and they use it to fulfill their hidden desires of themselves. These desires they cannot elucidate in front of people, but they always try to break the society's laws. This becomes the talk of the town. This Novel talks about How educated women use males for quid pro quo. A man of words who had certain dreams to come true became a puppet in the hands of society in the form of a successful woman. An evil society can force you to follow some illicit relationship. Sexuality is a biological and emotional process, but in the real world, it has become emotionless. This shows how emotionless we became and how our limbs are automatic. The Adam and Eve myths might be transformed because now all are sinners. This paper explores unspoken desires and their cultural impacts on traditional backgrounds. It also tries to curb the illicit emotions that can be a gateway to our downfall in our eyes.

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Introduction:

The novel talks about the modern world and its features, which are quite related to the harsh reality of life. Emotions and culture have no place in today's world. Many famous writers have written very famous books, like Vladimir Nabokov, D.H. Lawrence, Khushwant Singh, Salman Rushdie, etc. Some books are banned in society as they may corrupt society, or some mature minds need to understand their hidden meanings. These writers talk about some unspoken fields that are forbidden to share, such as Politics, sexuality, and social demerits. Society is a combination of creativity and criticism. The culture is depicted in many books, and it is a sheer mirror of society. How are lower-class laborers treated? They should have equal values and life expectancy. Seenu is the face of the driver community. They are hard-working and quite punctual in their respective jobs. The standard of living has dramatic differences between the rich and poor. Rich are masters and enjoy every meal according to time, and coffee has some serious value in their lives. Richa Pandit is a modern woman who adores herself physically and mentally. She is outspoken and bold while putting on the dresses in respective Indian cultures. She admires her appearance and tries to show some features to lure the man and society. She is like Belinda, who is getting ready and boasts her physicality and bodily features to incite the feelings of a man. It is a sheer representation of worldly things by her, such as pond cream and some costly cologne. It shows some artificial beauties who make us an autonomic character in real life. She is the face of most of the so-called intellectual women who are considered as highly respected due to their high background. They belong to rich families, and things are pretty easy for them, as food is on the table, and the roof is above their heads. The slogans of my body and my rules have devastated the society. It is not fit for women only; it is also related to men and masculinity. Women are free and should be free to do whatever they want to pursue in society. Even though the modern woman is successful and married, she is seeking sexual gratification in society. This is not an excuse to accept some illicit relationship. Richa Pandit was a kind woman, and she helped Abhilash, who is a student of M.com in Agra, with some money. He is down-to-earth and hard-working. He wants to be an I.A.S. officer. He could not afford the full burden of I.A.S. books. Richa helped him with his credit card, for instance. She rescues him from the loss of books, but she does

not follow the deep-rooted values of a married woman. Coffee houses play a major role in the setting of this novel; everything starts with coffee and a big bungalow. As we see 'A Game of Chess' in the Wasteland by T.S. Eliot, we see here the game of tennis. It was not just a game, but it was an incident that incited the feelings of both. Richa looked fabulous in what she put on, and she shone. She was well aware of her physical attributes; she kept an eye on Abhi while playing. She assumed that she would be examined by Abhi, and she cared about how she looked when she ran. She noticed she was being followed by Abhi's eyes as she played this game intensely. She knew she also had played this game with other mature men, but Abhi was unique because he was playing it professionally, and his stamina was unmatchable. She could not keep away her emotions and supported him. She was curious not about Abhi's study but how he observed her thighs and breathing sensation. She lost to him. It was not just about the game but her morality, and she was incited by unwanted desires of sexuality and worldly pleasure. She talks about shame and frustration if she was culturally right. She might have been a little upset, but she shook hands with him and agreed to go to a party and celebration. As Marie became the victim of her fate, Abhi was pulled into the same boat of fate. She was on the sled, and both of them went down morality and with some scary situations. Similarly, Abhi is tempted by her, and he agrees to be in the same boat as Marie. But he didn't know his fate would taste his identity in the house of Madame Richi. She was not ashamed of being French in front of a stranger whom she met in the public library. She didn't care about the loss of her cultural identity as she was enjoying the time being French with Abhi and happily married. He was in her house, or I should call it Bungalow. It was pleasantly big and had plenty of rooms. He could not control his emotions, and he was aroused sexually with a married woman. He was being a scholar and going to cope with the problems of society if he got through the I.A.S. exam. Abhi and Richa crossed the limits that society set for how they were going to justify their blender. They are both automated machines that are on for a certain time. There are no emotional feelings or cultural values. However, Abhi was innocent, and he was not the main lead controlling the motion of the relationship between them. He laid down with her, and he had no choice. He wanted a job and a house so he could stay in the city and overcome the expenses of his studies. He showed some serious intelligence while talking with Madam in a mischievous tone. He wanted to pay back as soon he got the money; he was honest, modest, and full of dreams. He tried to be worthy of it. He generously worked for the job and tried to be useful in the office accounting job. He has been a

go-getter in the field of education. He was showing seriousness in the field of education, as Madam provided him with upper empty room for study. However, both were on the wrong side of life as they were busy with merry-making and love affairs. Richa provided Abhi with her husband's clothes. She doesn't care about the presence of a stranger in her husband's clothes. She even compared him with the knight of the kingdom. This is quite strange as she is married, she is successful in life, and she is living happily. She went on and did not care about her modesty with Abhi; it was treated as a usual activity of the day. Richa was willing to surrender everything for the sake of hunger for pleasure. She is lost in search of bodily pleasure.

Identity Crisis of Male:

Abhi seemed to be a great student of general studies and raised concerns about the loss of water in the Yamuna River because dirt and chemical deposits had been dropped into the Yamuna from certain factories. The water in Yamuna is of the worst quality in Agra. He seemed to be a little worried and polite about the environmental hazards. However, later, he enjoyed the time with his Madame. He was living a life of dual face. He didn't like to drink, but later, he enjoyed the drink. He didn't mind being French with a married woman. The multiple uses of champagne are portrayed as a great deed of celebration. He came to be an I.A.S. officer but lost his morality and became a sinner. He accepted what was done by Adam and Eve was a sin and eventually went on the same path of sexual gratification. Richa was also in that conversation and became the same culprit in the hand of Satan. She knew how Adam was created, and later, the ribs of man paved the way for the creation of the first female on earth. She tasted the fruit of knowledge and lost the right to live in the Garden of Eden. She knew what the original sin was and that the fall of man started after that.

Fall of Female Identity:

Richa Pandit was discussing the inception of women while lying with Abhilash. This is just a satire on the modernity of people. She gave her husband's clothes to Abhilash, which signifies that she had merely replaced her husband with him. She commented borrowing and lending are enemies of good husbandry. She aroused him and treated him as her better wife. Richa Pandit could have saved Abhi and herself from the degradation of morality, but both of them went down with the flow of destiny. As the first woman was created from the ribs of the first man, she became the undistinctive part of a man. 'Frailty! thy name is woman!' This shows that She became a weak personality in the hands of circumstances. She became the

lady of shallot. She was detained in the four walls like golden shackles. She became weak and pitied; she felt hunger below the belt, and they both turned without much delay. It was hunger, as shown by 'Jayanta Mahapatra'. She lost her values, identity, and self-esteem to fulfill her hunger. She cared for her son, but she could not elucidate the real hurdles of her life to her husband. This is just merely a sketched rose on paper, a pretty flower and a symbol of love all over the world; incited the hidden desire of two couples, and they went down and down in their eyes. The idea comes first, but for good causes; it should not be for the degradation of morality and loss of self-cultural identity.

Cultural and Historical background:

The novel talks about the importance of knowledge through books. It shows the knowledge and new prospects that different books contain according to the genre of the theme. Books can share knowledge about politics, geography, and general knowledge. Books are revolutionary creations by human beings as they can veer the direction of people's mind-sets. Students read books for competition examinations, and they hunger for jobs. Some books are banned due to their explicit content, which might have a harsh impact on society. Books help in the process of becoming a higher administrator in society, and they attentively depict the face of the modern world. Many new genres have emerged in the post-colonial era; these provide information about revolution and the renaissance. It gives hope to mankind and adds some meaning to the value of lives. Many famous personalities, such as Dr Har Dayal, had very intellectual heredity because he had a photographic memory and could recite the books that he studied in his research. The research paper talks about how Abhi's life could be saved from the temptation of physical beauty. But Richa Pandit, being rich, almost bought the pleasure after paying prices; she paid for Abhilash's books and gave him a twenty-five thousand amount for an accountant job even though she made him her paying guest. Abhilash could be a victim due to the lack of money and the facilities he hoped for in his exam. That doesn't give a way to walk away from the sin he created with Richa. Eve was responsible for the first-ever sin, but not this time. Both would be equally blamed for diminishing the social and cultural aspects of Marriage. Abhilash was tempted towards Richa because it was his first interaction with a beautiful and modern female who gave him some space in her life. She became the lady of the boy. Destiny had it; it was fate that made it happen, as did her husband's disability. Richa fell for the curse of destiny and lost her self-identity. Sometimes, fate decides unexpected outcomes, and it paves the way for some unspoken aspects.

The relationship between them became a diminishing point in cultural status.

Conclusion:

The culture is deeply rooted in us. We follow our Hindustani culture, which was neglected many times in the novel. It has become the undistinguished part of our personality. We cannot ignore the true attire of an Indian. Love's Not Time's Fool deals with the themes of love affairs, identity crisis, and loss of self-existence. Richa Pandit becomes the foul part of the novel; she has not only devastated her life but also Abhilash's life, which has become a loss of identity. Abhilash was struggling with economic conditions. He became the culprit in the hand of time, which fools both of them. Both of them became the reason for the fall of man. Richa Pandit portrays the bold and modern character of a successful yet passionate woman about sexual desires. She hides her son from her husband, and due to his impotent disability, she is entangled in a love affair with Abhilash. She, being a widow, remarried Abhilash, which shows the fighting spirits of modern women. They lost the value of character and self-dignity. However, in the end, they regain consciousness; they socially accumulate in a pious relationship. In this paper, we have observed that an effort was made to shed some light on how to face arduous social and financial conditions. This novel is a true representation and criticism of life. This novel incites some serious issues with the environment, water pollution, and the condition of widows, orphans, and old people. In our attempt, false love, extra-marital affairs, and loss of identity were examined. Love's not Time's Fool is based on what it projects through its title; love cannot be bound within the premises of any physical quantity, and time cannot object to the commencement of love. The decline of self-identity has been a major theme in the writings of a post-modern era. Prof. Vikas Sharma portrayed the real agony and pain through Richa Pandit and Abhilash. There are some unsung issues that need to be eradicated from society. In the 21st century, feelings and emotions have no space in relationships. We must follow our ancestors to avoid the outcome of Doom's day. As in 1922, predicted by T.S. Eliot, there is a linear degradation of morality and self-identity. We must go under the red rock. The church's bell is calling. Only there we can find solace for the welfare of mankind. Life has challenges, but we must not veer from the direction of our inner tranquillity to get momentous pleasure. We must follow the path of Datta, Dayadhvam, and Damyata. This is the path of Shantih.

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